

SURPASS

And its packaging film

SURPASS research project. Recycle packaging while ensuring consumer safety.

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Plastic packaging films generate significant waste that must be reduced and better managed. The SURPASS project is a research project funded by the Horizon Europe program of the European Commission. It includes a case study on packaging films used to thermoform packaging trays. Thanks to MNL (Multi-NanoLayers) manufacturing technology, the SURPASS team hopes to obtain recyclable packaging films with very good barrier properties. This MNL technology makes it possible to extrude films with a structure of very thin layers of plastic material combined with a part that has the function of a functional barrier. The role of this barrier is to prevent the passage of contaminants into the food and thus protect the consumer. It is important that the development of a recyclable solution is done while maintaining consumer protection functionalities. This is precisely the wish of the SURPASS project team. In order to confirm the performances achieved by the packaging film, SURPASS chose to carry out an overall evaluation.

This is the "Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)" system proposed by the Join Research Center of the European Commission. The packaging film will be evaluated over the entire life cycle. The evaluation will be multi-criteria with the evaluation of substances at risk for health and ecosystems, that of environmental impacts by the practice of Life Cycle Analysis, and that of economic performance with the analysis of the cost of the cycle of life (CCV or Life Cycle Cost - LCC). Find all the details on <https://www.surpass-project.eu/>